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Project Planning: A Study of Sustainable Materials Procurement

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ABSTRACT

This research proposal aimed to contribute to the understanding of how, through sustainable material procurement in the construction industry, the social responsibility of construction projects can be enhanced. From the review of the literature, research on this subject is expedient because the status quo in the construction industry is such that the materials commonly used for construction projects have far-reaching social, economic, and environmental implications. It was revealed that the implications of sustainable procurement are multi-dimensional—social, economic, and economic. However, the practical strategies to be used to tackle challenges encountered in the processes of integrating sustainability in construction project planning and the metrics that determine sustainable construction projects are some highlighted under-explored areas. The research proposes a combination of interpretivist and positivist research philosophies and a mixed-methods approach. It is also suggested that online surveys and semi-structured interviews with key players within the construction industry will be appropriate for data collection for the research. Furthermore, to analyse data, convergent data analysis would be generally employed, while exploratory data analysis would be used specifically for quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative data. The study recommends that further research can explore case study research and comparative analysis routes.

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CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction.

This chapter is foundational to the subsequent chapters; it captures the background to the proposed research, the rationale for conducting the research, and a declaration of the aim and objectives of the research. Importantly, the chapter also outlines the structure of this extended research proposal.

1.1 Background and Context

Environmental sustainability and social responsibility have become prominent and prevailing global movements in the 21st century (Karwowski & Raulinajtys-Grzybek 2021), Rehman et al (2022) highlights that the growing awareness of environmental and social challenges is what has chiefly given rise to the increasing campaign for environmental sustainability and social responsibility practices across various industries and sectors. The drastic changes in climate, excessive waste emissions, land degradation, and deforestation are major challenges that pose a serious threat to ecological diversity, causing many countries to be concerned about their potential environmental effect (Salem et al. 2018; Sarfraz 2023).

In a similar vein, Latapí et al. (2019) report that the movement for social responsibility was sparked by, among other things, the social ideals of a community, ethical concerns, environmental concerns, and social inequality issues. These contributions indicate that the principles of sustainability and social responsibility are intertwined (Meseguer-Sánchez 2021). Sustainability and social responsibility are also emerging discussions under project management, emphasis have been levied extensively on its place

in project planning and execution (Marten and Carvalho 2017). Concerns about resource exhaustion, waste management or its outright prevention, and the over-engagement of multiple stakeholders in projects, as well as the necessity to strike a balance between economic goals with environmental and social goals are some of the factors leading up to advocacies for the integration of social responsibility and sustainability within project management (Marten and Carvalho 2017).

The activities carried out by several industries have prominent impacts on the environment, the society and on the economy (Basiago 1998). According to Yu et al (2018), studies have shown that the construction industry continues to have a significant impact on the environment and a higher energy consumption rate when compared with other industries. Yan et al. (2016) also maintain that the very nature of the operations and activities of the construction industry is such that its impact on the environment is prominent. Santamouris and Feng (2018) further posit that approximately 36 percent of the world's energy is consumed by the buildings and construction sector. More so, the 2020 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction (2020) revealed that the building and construction industry was responsible for 39% of the process-based carbon dioxide emissions.

Gangoells et al. (2009) asserted that the industry's activities permeates various spheres of influence including the social, environmental, economic, and political spheres, among others. In addition to this, several aspects of the activities of the construction industry involve environmental threatening activities such as deforestation, land degradation, and waste emissions, all of which are core environmental issues (Opoku et al. 2022). Chang et al. (2016) put forward that the interactions of construction with multiple stakeholders such as the government, communities and businesses have the potential to increase the industry's overall impact on the society both directly and indirectly.

Furthermore, Hossain et al. (2020) in a critique of the construction industry argued that generally, construction projects require extensive resource consumption, leading to a possibility of resource depletion. This is a fundamental concern because the natural resources of the earth are not inexhaustible (Rockström et al. 2013). Therefore, Karunasena, Rathnayake, and Senarathne's (2016) argument is that factors such as the foregoing accentuate the fact that sustainable construction will go a mile to preserve the environment for future generations.

Utam (2020) also put forward the argument that sustainability in the construction industry is a necessity because the industry needs to ready itself for foreseeable prospects associated with the alterations necessitated in design, construction, and management. The requirement to proactively address these environmental and social concerns necessitate the introduction of rules, regulations, policies, and demands that can compel the construction industry to adopt sustainable and socially responsible practices (Lam et al. 2016).

On consideration of all these lapses, it is evident that construction project planning should involve more sustainable and socially responsible policies and practices that projects positively its environmental and social responsibility stance. As a result, Naoum and Egbu (2016) propose that sustainable material procurement is very instrumental in addressing this challenge because it goes a long way in determining the overall performance of the construction project. The emphasis of the authors is that there is a relationship between material procurement and the realisation of sustainable and socially responsible construction projects.

Kashkool (2014) argues that more often than not, the materials used for many construction projects such as steel, wood or cement have significant carbon footprints or generate greenhouse gas emissions. The outcome of the construction projects therefore hinges largely on the sort of materials used (Ajayi and Oyedele 2018). In the same light, Xia et al. (2018) posit that materials procurement in the construction sector also involve social

concerns such as ethical labour relations between the suppliers, employers and employees; concerns on the health and safety of the workers and the community at large; concerns around sourcing of materials locally; and plurality and inclusion considerations.

Hence, Khan et al. (2018) suggest that a combination of the environmental impact of construction projects, its adaptability to shifting climatic trends, and its potential to either promote or decline social and economic well-being are all significantly influenced by the materials used during the execution of construction projects.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research is to investigate the manner in which sustainable material procurement guarantees the seamless integration of social responsibility and sustainability principles into the planning of construction projects. Therefore, to achieve this aim, the objectives of the research are to:

1. Assess the current state of the construction industry, highlighting the social, economic and environmental dimensions of construction projects.
2. Evaluate the current attitude of the construction industry to social responsibility and Sustainability practices.
3. Consider how sustainable methods of material procurement affect the sociological, ecological, and economic aspects of construction projects.
4. Identify the principal stakeholders in construction projects and evaluate how they contribute to the procurement of sustainable materials.
5. Analyse the obstacles stakeholders faced while implementing sustainable material procurement initiatives within construction projects and offer suggestions.

6. Describe the standards used to assess the extent of the integration of sustainable and socially responsible material procurement practises into construction projects.

1.3 Rationale for the Study

Oladirin, Ogunsemi and Aje (2012) put forward the argument that it is evident that in various nations, the construction industry plays a substantial role in fostering the economic development of the country. Khaertdinova et al. (2021) characterized the construction sector as a source of numerous employment prospects across various stages of project development, encompassing design, procurement, and construction phases within the industry. According to Liu et al (2020), the construction industry is a great economic booster, such that when the construction industry thrives, the economy of the country has a higher proclivity to thrive better. They averred that this is the case because the industry attracts the bulk of investments a country can boast of and the more the investments, the better the economy of the nation.

Unfortunately, the industry is bewildered by a negative reputation of its lack of or poor sustainable and socially responsible practices. The construction industry is reportedly the highest waste producing industry because of poor management of the process of extracting, producing and transporting construction materials which engender waste emissions (Opoku et al. 2022). Fathalizadeh et al. (2019) then expounds that the waste produced by construction project processes becomes a threat to the environment and eventually to the health of people within that community.

Despite these, the construction industry is still lacking of a comprehensive and enforceable industrial standards or benchmarks for the effective management of waste all through the project life cycle (Ajayi 2017). However, Xia et al. (2018) posited that the regulatory bodies of many countries are becoming more aware of the threats involved and are consequently gradually emphasizing the importance of sustainability and

social responsibilities across industries. Hence companies that align with these requirements tend to have a competitive edge Cantele and Zardini (2018).

The research would show how sustainability and social responsibility practices can be introduced to construction projects through sustainable materials procurement. Holistically, the necessity to link the construction sector with environmental and socially responsible practises serves as the primary justification for this study. Therefore, conducting this research will contribute to the body of knowledge on this subject area, and would also be beneficial for reforms in the construction industry. Project management professionals, stakeholders in the construction industry and across other industries, policy makers, and the general public can also benefit from the outcome and recommendations from this research.

1.4 Structure of the Research Proposal.

The proposal is segmented into 4 chapters, the instant chapter has been able to introduce the subject of the research by presenting some background information which sets the stage for following chapters. The chapter also explains the rationale for the research, as well as the central aim and consequent objectives of the study.

Chapter two is the literature review section of the proposal, this chapter will cover a rich review of existing research and core theoretical frameworks on the subjects of sustainability, social responsibility, and material procurement within the construction industry.

Chapter three presents the suitable methodology approach for the research. This covers the proposed research design, methods, philosophy, data collection methods, and the planned methods for analysis. The chapter will also include details on the limitations and the ethical considerations of the research.

The final chapter presents a summary of the cogent aspects of each of the chapters of research and recommendations for further research.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

In recent times, the concepts of social responsibility and sustainability in the construction industry have captured the attention of many researchers in the academic and business world. This is chiefly due to the increasing global attention accorded the improving of measures to facilitate the reduction and management of climate change, land degradation, deforestation, air pollution, and other pressing environmental concerns. Hence, this chapter delves into a review of relevant literature that address the concepts of sustainability, social responsibility, material procurement, and sustainable material procurement in construction projects.

The review is structured in a way that aligns with the aim and objectives of this research. Therefore, it covers an overview of the construction industry, the theoretical framework surrounding these concepts, the integration of sustainability through sustainable material procurement, as well as the role of and the challenges faced by stakeholders involved in the process. Importantly, this section identifies the gaps in the existing literature that this study specifically aims to address.

2.2 Overview of the Construction Industry

The construction industry has been described as a sector within the manufacturing industry that encompasses activities such as the building, renovation and maintenance of infrastructure (Torgautov et al. 2021). According to Ajayi (2017), the construction industry is a highly project-oriented industry, wherein a bulk of the industry's projects drive towards satisfying client needs within a system of financial, material, and logistical constraints. Padala, Maheswari, and Hirani (2022) classify the

types of construction projects into structural and service projects. Structural being residential projects, while service being commercial projects, industrial projects and institutional projects. Safa (2015) extended the classification to include transportation projects, telecommunication projects and power plant construction, among several others.

Olarenwaju and Abdul-Aziz (2015) in their research on the general features of the construction industry indicated that the majority of construction projects involve some form of excavation and foundation work that deal directly with certain natural elements of the earth even though they may vary in nature, size or complexity. Pheng and Hou (2019) also outline the general activities of the construction industry to include processes from extraction and production of raw materials, manufacturing of building materials, project planning, design, and execution. Hence, their core argument is that construction activities typically begin long before the physical execution of the project; execution is just the climax of a combination of preliminary processes that lead up to it.

Furthermore, a plethora of authors including Sayidganiev, Karimbaev, and Achilov (2022), Li et al. (2019), Arshad et al. (2017), and Kama et al. (2012), among several others have argued that there is a strong nexus between the construction industry and the economy of a nation; that the industry occupies a revered position in the economy of any nation. Dang and Pheng (2015) specifically describe construction as intrinsically an economic activity in itself. It has been described as a reliable signifier that the economy of a country is progressing. A sound construction sector will definitely boost the country's economic outlook (Kamal et al. 2012).

Venugopal et al. (2020) expounded this thought further with the argument that construction projects create more job avenues, contribute directly to the economy and facilitates the smooth running of commercial activities within the economy. With such an impact, the worldwide construction output for the year 2020 was estimated at US\$10.7 trillion according to the

Oxford Economics Global Construction Perspectives, and it is anticipated to rise to an astounding US\$13.3 trillion by 2025. Therefore, the construction industry must consistently be looked into to ensure that it is living up to these high expectations and progressing optimally for the betterment of the country's economy.

Source: Global Construction Perspectives, Oxford Economics

Figure 2.1 Global Construction Perspectives, Oxford Economics

Furthermore, Olarenwaju and Abdul-Aziz (2015) also examined the interrelationship of the construction industry with other industries, they highlight that the industry does not stand alone but is very much interrelated with other industries, and this feature makes the activities

carried out within the industry far-reaching. Moavenzadeh (2022) sheds better light on this by evidencing that the industry covers a wide spectrum of projects such as residential projects, infrastructural, institutional or commercial projects which spread across several sectors of the economy. Ajayi (2017) argues that the results produced by the construction sector, encompassing both public and private constructions including structures, roadways, other transport systems, dams, canals, and bridges, are crucial to maintaining the continued viability of the global economy and supporting the sustainability of numerous sectors.

The far-reaching impacts of the industry imply that promoting sustainability within the industry especially as it relates to the wide spectrum of projects in the industry will have a consequent positive impact on other related sectors and industries.

2.3 Environmental, Social, and Economic Impacts of Construction Projects.

In the different studies conducted by Nagapan, Rahman, and Asmi (2011), Ijigah et al (2013) and in the more recent studies of Banihashemi et al. (2021) and Tafesse, Girma, and Dessalegn, (2022) on the construction industry, it is argued by the authors that the implementation and execution of construction projects reportedly have significant environmental, social and economic implications.

2.3.1 Environmental Impacts

Nagapan, Rahman, and Asmi (2011), Ijigah et al (2013) submit that environmental threats such as natural habitat destruction, air pollution/ozone layer depletion, environmental depletion, ecological disruption, water pollution, and land degradation are common environmental implications traceable to construction-related activities. According to a study by Polat et al. (2017), between 10 and 30 percent of the waste dumped to landfills worldwide is attributable to construction

waste. Likewise, in a study by Luangcharoenrat et al. (2019), the energy consumption of the construction industry was pegged at 35% and pegged at 40% for the discharge of carbon dioxide. The research carried out by Ijigah et al (2013) buttresses this fact with an explanation that the physical execution of projects in the industry need power for the equipment, machines, and lighting to run, and the consumption of petrol as well as other energy sources by large machinery directly leads to air pollution. In the same light, Ametepey and Ansah (2014) identify construction project activities such as excavation, land clearing and grading to directly lead to environmental depletion.

2.3.2 Social Implications

The arguments of Tafesse, Girma, and Dessalegn, (2022) and Aslam, Huang and Cui (2020) are that construction projects also have social implications because the process leading up to many projects directly affect certain aspects of the well-being of host communities. Jiang and Wong (2016) explained social impact in the light of the establishment of infrastructure by the construction industry which in turn affects the daily lifestyle and activities of people. According to the Interorganizational Committee on Guidelines and Principles for Social Impact Assessment (1995) social impact is defined as "...the consequences to human populations of any public or private actions-that alter the ways in which people live, work, play, relate to one another, organize to meet their needs, and generally cope as members of society."

Therefore, according to Aboginije et al. (2020), the main societal effects of construction waste include health concerns from a range of diseases caused by the poor waste management of construction wastes, issues of transportation congestion, disagreements with construction companies, blocking of drainages, causing floods, and garbage spread by rainfall. Patil and Laishram (2016) added that issues related to land acquisition such as forceful or wrongful acquisition, and displacement of local residents are

also prominent social impacts of construction projects. Goel, Ganesh and Kaur (2019) claim that compared to other major industries, construction workers have a fifty percent greater likelihood of occupational injury or death due to the risks it entails. These environmental, social and economic issues consequently point to the necessity for social responsibility principles to be incorporated in construction project planning.

2.3.3 Economic Implications

Another dimension of the impact of construction projects is the economic dimension. According to Dang and Pheng, (2015), since construction itself has been described as an economic activity, it therefore inherently has a substantial impact on the economy of countries. While the positive impacts on the economy have been discussed exhaustively, Fadiya, Georgakis and Chinyio, (2014) give insight into its negative impacts in their study on the quantitative analysis of the sources of construction waste. They highlighted the challenge of having to gather additional costs to manage the waste production of construction projects as a fundamental economic implication of construction projects. Yeheyis et al (2013) argues that one of the biggest reasons for economic decline and failing companies in the construction sectors is the poor management of construction projects by the stakeholders involved. In a research by Mhetre, Konnur, and Landage (2016) and that by Gyamfi, Aigbavboa and Thwala (2022), both researches contend that running construction projects and the allocation of investment to them involve inherently high levels of risk. Therefore, these environmental, social and economic impacts of construction projects amplify the need for increased intentionality all through the phases of construction projects. This is essential to mitigate the adverse environmental, social and economic effects associated with the projects. The diagram coined below provides a diagrammatic representation of a summary of the afore-explained impacts of construction projects.

Figure 2.2 social economic and environmental impacts of construction projects

Source: Adapted from *Ijigah et al (2013); Aslam, Huang and Cui (2020); Dang and Pheng (2015)*

2.4 Social responsibility and Sustainability in the Construction Industry

The evolution of the concepts of social responsibility and sustainability are generally a response to the environmental and social issues related to projects implementation, according to Yevdokimova (2018). Marques (2016) recorded that discussions on regarding whether businesses had any obligations to society sparked the social responsibility movement. Generally, social responsibility flows from the ethical expectations that individuals, businesses or organizations have to have the benefit and wellbeing of the society at heart when carrying out their activities (Marques, 2016).

2.4.1 Conceptual Analysis of Social responsibility and Sustainability

Within the context of this research, Sustainability is used to connote environmental sustainability and sustainable development. Ruggerio (2021) explained that both concepts of sustainability and sustainable development have been used interchangeably because of they are closely related, hence their definitions are also nebulous. However, Giovannoni and Fabietti (2013) described sustainability to encompass sustainable development, it was described as the responsible use of resources in such a way that the ecosystem is preserved, promotes social well-being and secures posterity of coming generations so that they can satisfy their needs. The emphasis of this description is that it entails a social, environmental and economic balance.

The release of the "Our Common Future," publication also referred to as the Brundtland Report published in 1987 introduced and solidified sustainable development as an essential pillar of international development. According to Hajian and Kashani (2021), initially, sustainable development was considered as a means of avoiding ecological disruption occasioned by the profit-seeking misuse of resources and the degradation of the environment. The main emphasis was on keeping the environment excellent. But, the idea has now been extended to harmonize economic and social complexities.

Murray and Dainty (2009) define corporate social responsibility refers to an organization's responsibility for the effects of its corporate actions on the different stakeholder groups it engages with, such as its customers, employees, and communities, as well as the environment. Jonkutė, Staniškis, and Dukauskaitė (2011) explain that the principle of social responsibility is commonly believed to be a vital instrument used to establish sustainability, making both concepts intertwined.

Kleine and Hauff (2009) in their article on the implementation of corporate social responsibility through the application of sustainability strategies

asserted that the principles are not mutually exclusive, hence, companies must infuse them into their core values to improve their competitive position and foster a positive societal impact. Also, Kumar and Sundararajan (2019) state in their study that social responsibility can help companies achieve social objectives, promote economic prosperity, and enhance environmental preservation. However, to achieve this, it must be effectively contained within prevailing sustainable development strategies to secure a future that is more inclusive, egalitarian, and sustainable.

2.4.2 Sustainability and Social Responsibility in the Construction Industry

Within the construction industry, sustainability and social responsibility are core principles to be considered. This fact is heightened by the environmental, social and economic impact of construction projects. For instance, the "Building Responsible Competitiveness" project which was funded by the European Commission in 2010, resulted in the creation of the four primary Sustainability areas that contractors are expected to adhere to including- health and safety, eco-compatibility, supply, and equal opportunity. These facets accentuate the importance of the integration of social responsibility and environmental sustainability into the construction sector.

Jiang and Wong (2016) in their study on the key areas of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in the construction industry, linked social responsibility with the competitive prowess of a construction company on the elucidation that in contemporary times, for the company to gain and sustain its competitive advantage, it must be viewed as a company that responds with greater competence to client concerns regarding project goals as well as being able to satisfy social expectations and retain a positive reputation in the community.

Along the same lines, Bal et al. (2013) posits that the integration of sustainability and social responsibility in construction projects is a key performance indicator (kpi) for competitive construction companies. Murray

and Cotgrave (2007) also proposed that the sustainability paradigm be employed as a lens through which construction performance may be judged, taking into account the scale and importance of the construction sector to the global economy and its overall impact on the environment.

In a survey conducted by Goh, and Rowlinson (2023) on the relevance of the incorporation of sustainable practices into activities in the construction industry, the results indicate that beyond the environmental benefits it generates, economic benefits will also be derived from sustainable construction projects encompassing the reductions in energy expenses and the receipt of green subsidies for sustainable and socially responsible construction projects.

2.5 Stakeholder Roles in Sustainability and Social responsibility Integration in construction projects

According to Freeman (1984), a project stakeholder is a person or group of people who have an impact on or have the power to have an impact on the project. As noted earlier, studies show that the construction industry does not stand alone because many construction projects contribute greatly to the sustainability of other sectors (Olarenwaju and Abdul-Aziz 2015; Ajayi 2017). For that reason, the planning and execution of construction projects will practically involve the engagement of many stakeholders across other sectors and industries.

For instance, Srinivasan and Dhivya (2020) list Project managers, Consultants, Contractors, Construction workers, the Government, Engineers, Architects, Surveyors, the communities, and connected Agencies or Bodies as all stakeholders involved in different phases of construction. Prabhu (2016) further classifies the stakeholders involved in construction projects broadly into internal and external stakeholders with internal stakeholders being those that influence construction projects directly and external stakeholders being those who indirectly influence construction projects.

Bal et al. (2013) advanced the idea that while the stakeholders involved in construction projects are numerous, they can however be narrowed down according to the nature and size of the specific construction project. They argue that the project type and size will determine those that would be involved in it as stakeholders. The authors therefore propose that for the integration of sustainability, a thorough and intentional identification procedure is crucial in establishing a boundary between the stakeholders who will be involved and those who would not.

Lin et al. (2017) advance the idea that there are variations in the capacities of stakeholders to exert impact on construction project's social responsibility. According to them, among the stakeholders involved, governments, contractors, and developers emerge as potent players, whereas communities, NGOs, and end users exhibit relatively constrained influence. Nevertheless, the authors contend that the strategies employed by these stakeholders to wield their influence towards accomplishing their objectives remains nebulous.

According to Goh and Rowlinson (2023), projecting the economic value inherent in sustainable construction projects will help improve stakeholder engagement in the process. The authors claim that through adopting what they tag an "integrated project delivery" (IPD) viewpoint, construction stakeholders will gain a comprehensive understanding to assess the true economic value of sustainable construction projects by taking their prospective cost effectiveness into account.

Bal et al (2013) also put forward an argument that incorporating sustainability in construction projects will involve all the stakeholders all through their engagement in the construction process. According to him, the process of their engagement involves six (6) stages vis a vis identifying them based on the nature and size of the project, relating them with the sustainability target based on their respective skills-set, prioritising them based on their potential impact on project success, managing the relationship to meet stakeholder expectation, measuring their performance

to improve efficiency and putting target into action through plans that ensure that the sustainability targets are met.

Figure 2.3 Project Stakeholder Engagement Process
al. (2013)

Source: Bay et

2.6 Sustainable Material Procurement for Construction Projects

Ruparathna and Hewage (2015) defines procurement in this context as acquiring the items and services needed for organizational goals while ensuring affordability, quality, and timeliness, without harming the environment or society. According to the authors, procurement operations encompass a spectrum extending from the recognition of necessities to the culmination of projects, thereby presenting an ideal avenue for amalgamating organizational strategic trajectories. As per the definition offered by the Green Council in 2010, green procurement entails acquiring goods or services that diminish or produce favourable environmental

effects. Thus, it involves the incorporation of ecological considerations into key procurement approaches, guidelines, and instructions. It encompasses applying renewable resources, recycled materials and other responsible material procurement practices. Material procurement is therefore a crucial component of the construction planning stage of construction projects. Yu, Yevu, and Nani (2020) state that in the realm of construction, procurement involves the acquisition of resources and services throughout the complete lifespan of construction endeavours. This progressively influences the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In their research, Wong, Chan and Wadu (2016) advance the idea that facilitating the widespread use of sustainable materials procurement for constructing projects has been a key issue in the construction industry due to the pressing need to improve industry practises in a green, secure, and cost-effective way. They suggest that encouraging environmental-friendly procurement for construction processes will involve cogent factors such as satisfying client expectations, complying with required environmental regulations that function to alleviate adverse environmental concerns associated with construction, and satisfying requirements of Non-Governmental Organizations on social environmental and economic basis.

Likewise, Opoku et al. (2022) also argues that sustainable procurement within the construction realm strives to foster societal and financial advantages for those involved in the project, all this while also mitigating harm to the environment. This involves an approach where project stakeholders align with design and development requisites, concurrently achieving optimal utilisation of resources across the project's entirety.

A study by Bohari et al (2020) tie sustainable material procurement to the control of the key players involved in construction processes. The authors contend that the core values of stakeholders such as, technical capabilities commitment, mindfulness and proper information distribution are key factors that are also very instrumental in fostering sustainable material procurement within the industry. In the study conducted by Bohari et al.

(2019), it is emphasized that the existence of guidelines that endorse ecologically-aware procurement, and the incorporation of environmentally-friendly criteria within the process of seeking proposals or bids from potential suppliers, builders, or service providers to meet project needs, while duly acknowledging the importance of responsible purchasing, fosters sustainable procurement practices.

Berry (2011) claim that there are certain factors that drive sustainable procurement including the values of the organisation, marketing, risk control, the goodwill of stakeholder and cost effectiveness. These drivers play a big role in why construction businesses and organisations choose will sustainable materials. These powerful forces give strong reasons to adopt sustainable practices and make them a part of how they run their operations by making the economic, environment and societal benefits more apparent.

Figure 2.4: Drivers of Sustainable Procurement (Source: Berry, 2011)

According to Ruparathna & Hewage (2015), the primary benefit of adopting sustainable procurement is the realisation of cost savings over an extended duration. Moreover, there are supplementary advantages, including mitigating the adverse impact of hazardous goods on public health, thereby

ensuring societal welfare and safeguarding community rights. Just as the impact of construction projects is multi-dimensional; having social, environmental and economic dimensions, the studies of Berry (2011), Komolafe (2022) also present the idea that sustainable material procurement essentially address these social, economic, and environmental concerns. They illustrated this notion in the table presented below.

Environmental issues	Social issues	Economic issues
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Release of substances into the atmosphere • Effluents discharged into water bodies • Releases onto land • Consumption of raw materials and natural resources • Energy consumption • Water consumption • Released energy • Residues and waste products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging a varied array of competitive suppliers • Cultivating equitable working conditions • Strengthening the workforce (such as health and security, the freedom to form or join a union) • Enabling training opportunities and skill development • Advantages for the local community • Ethical and just procurement approaches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of employment opportunities • Comprehensive ownership costs • Optimizing returns on investment funds • Supporting small and medium-sized businesses • Reducing barriers to entry • Ensuring the continuity of viable business operations for job creation • Ensuring supplier reliability through fair and competitive agreements to sustain business viability.

Table 2.1: Key social, economic, and environmental concerns addressed by sustainable procurement. Source: Berry (2011), Komolafe (2022)

2.7 Challenges and Barriers to Sustainable Material Procurement

Ershadi et al (2021) summarised the barriers into intra organisational and extra- organisational barriers, intra-organisational referring to the barriers within an organisation it focuses on how organizations handle sustainability using their internal methods, systems, and resources. The extra-organisational domain centres on external stakeholders and their influence on sustainability efforts.

2.7.1 Lack of Unified Perspective

A research by Ruparathna and Hewage (2015) sheds light on a notable challenge within the construction industry's dynamics — the prevalent absence of a unified viewpoint concerning procurement as a project process. The core of their research exposed the lapse in terms of the absence of an unanimously shared perspective among professionals and stakeholders on the process of procurement in a lie cycle of a project. In a similar line, Álvarez, Zartha and Orozco (2019) argue that there are differing opinions among stakeholders about what sustainability values entail and these divergent views makes productive collaborations among stakeholders for effective integration of sustainable procurement a challenge.

2.7.2 Cost/ Financial Implication

In a study carried out by Goh, Su, and Rowlinson (2023), they discovered that while the endeavours to promote sustainability have intensified, the integration of sustainability into mainstream construction projects remains far from widespread. According to them, the recurring impediment in the journey towards better implementation of sustainable practices within construction projects is the lack of sufficient financial resources to soldier its cost implications. Construction projects are already very capital intensive due to the high cost of regulatory compliance, high labour costs, and expensive construction materials, equipment and machinery (Stasiak-Betlejewska and Potkány 2015). Hence, according to Hald, Wiik and

Larssen (2021), sustainable materials procurement also have high financial cost considerations.

2.7.3 Unclear Stakeholder Responsibilities

Lin et al (2019) and Zhou and Mi (2017) emphasize that within the context of project sustainability and societal obligations, a conspicuous aspect meriting in-depth exploration pertains to the unclear demarcation of stakeholder responsibilities. They postulated that the success of efforts aimed at sustainable material procurement runs the risk of being weakened by the lack of clearly defined roles and duties among stakeholders. Attaining sustainable materials procurement would involve the combined efforts of suppliers, contractors, designers, and end-users, therefore, in instances where the delineation of stakeholder roles remains indistinct, repercussions encompassing perplexity, ineffective communication, and a dearth of responsibility may ensue, thereby jeopardizing the fulfilment of sustainable material procurement objectives.

2.7.4 Poor Awareness in Under-developed and Developing Countries.

Brammer and Walker (2011) claim that despite the rising attention of researchers to the subject of sustainable materials procurement in construction projects, many of these research are focused only on developed countries. The implication of this is that developing countries continue to make use of unsustainable materials to build their economy, thus, in the event of time when the idea of sustainable materials is sold to them, they remain reluctant. More so, diverse circumstances and issues might necessitate customised methodologies and approach. Ogunsanya et al. (2022) also argued that the low levels of sustainability awareness impedes its adoption.

2.7.5 Government interference

Since the construction sector is a major contributor to the overall economy, it is often regulated by the government (Aniekwu 2004). Ogunsanya et al. (2022) highlighted that there are existing problems with transparency in

the government of many nations as it relates to sustainability in the construction industry. They explained that the interferences of the Government causes mismatches between procurement strategies and national sustainability policies, and leads to conflicts, diverting attention from sustainability goals.

2.7.6 Short-Term Thinking

About 104 professionals from the Australian and New Zealand building supply chains participated in a research survey performed by Loosemore and Lim (2017) and the findings reveal that short-term thinking in corporate social responsibility actions within construction hampers sustainable material procurement. They also argued that a bulk of corporate social responsibility initiatives often focus only on isolated environmental concerns, lacking a broad and comprehensive approach needed for successful sustainable material procurement in construction.

2.7.7 Complexities of the Construction Industry

Han, Skibniewski, and Wang (2017) elucidate that the construction industry is complex and involves many different aspects and this can make it difficult for procurement managers to find the right resources and subcontractors. Thus, this poses as a barrier because they often have limited choices when deciding where to get what they need for a project. Explains that project complexities is what accounts for the complexity of the industry. He argued that before sustainable practices can thrive within the industry, there must first be proper understanding of project complexity. Govindan, Shankar, and Kannan (2016) and Khoshnava et al. (2018) also argue that the selection of Green Building Materials (GBM) must take into account every sustainability factor, which is a decision based on multiple factors that calls for mathematical methodologies like the multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) method.

2.7.8 Policy Barriers

Sourani and Sohail (2011) argued that the regulatory framework for the construction industry is another major barrier to sustainable practise and policies in many countries. They explained that the absence of comprehensive regulatory framework in some countries, or complex and nebulous frameworks for some other countries both stifle the integration of sustainable practices.

Figure 2.5: The barriers to sustainable procurement management
Source: Ershadi (2021)

2.8 Theoretical perspectives

The theoretical framework for a research refers to the underlying theories, concepts, and models that help to establish an in-depth understanding of the research focus and gives direction to the research (Lederman, and Lederman, 2015). For a research on the integration of social responsibility into construction project planning through sustainable material procurement, the relevant and core theoretical perspectives that are cogent to the understanding of the research are considered below.

2.8.1 Stakeholder Theory

One of the primary management frameworks used to explore social responsibility issues in companies is the stakeholder theory. Parmar et al (2010) explains that this theoretical approach is grounded in the notion that organizations do not operate in isolation; instead, they are intricately linked with a variety of stakeholders who possess some form of interests in the endeavour depending on the level of their engagement. According to Freeman (2010), the core concepts of stakeholder theory are value generation, trade, and effective business management.

Hörisch, Freeman and Schaltegger (2014) explained that in the context of sustainable material procurement, the theory shows how important it is to consider the different stakeholder concerns, their engagement, and how it affects them during the procurement process. Yang, Zou and Wang (2016) advanced the notion that it would take only the cooperation of the network of stakeholders engaged in construction projects to manage the risks associated with the construction projects in a way that ensures sustainable green construction development processes. In a study by Lin et al. (2019) the authors state that the network of stakeholders involved in construction projects influence themselves. They explained that the diverse approaches employed by various project stakeholders helps them exert mutual influence on each other towards accomplishing goals in a socially responsible manner.

Despite the positive appraisals of the theory, Clifton and Amran (2011) posit that the stakeholder theory, akin to other management theories, has encountered significant critique for its pronounced concentration on economic value generation centred on corporations, which at times sidelines wider sustainability considerations and human-oriented viewpoints. Furthermore, Freeman (2015) averred that due to the narrowed focus of the theory on management, the involvement of external forces like rules and market dynamics may be overlooked under the stakeholder theory, which could place an undue amount of responsibility on organisations to manage stakeholders' interests.

2.8.2 Triple Bottom Line Approach (TBL)

Coined by Elkington, Goh et al (2020) describes the triple bottom line (TBL) as a complete system used to measure how well organizations perform in three main areas: social, environmental, and economic. Instead of just looking at money-making, the TBL considers a wider range of effects and outcomes as it goes beyond short-term profits to address how businesses can be responsible and sustainable over time in different ways. Although initially an accounting concept (Elkington, 1994), TBL has progressed to also apply to the process of instituting sustainable development. In present times, sustainability is more about the triple bottom line of people, prosperity, and the planet (GMP, 2019), these 3 P's have become the pillars for modern sustainability policies. Gachie (2019) introduced the Sustainability Compliance Index as a new paradigm for quantifying TBL; businesses can use this to help with implementation by making sure TBL is integrated strategically into all processes from planning and material procurement.

2.8.3 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)

EIA is typically seen as a tool that empowers authorities to decide whether to approve a project and to specify the requirements that must be met for project approval. Uttam et al. (2013) put forward that interlinking environmental impact assessment with sustainable material procurement

will increase the integration of sustainable material procurement in construction projects. They explained that by assessing and reducing the environmental impacts they have through impact assessments, it guarantees that construction projects are environmentally sustainable and correspond to the values of green procurement. Morgan (2012) proposed that environmental impact assessment should cover project planning and design phases in addition to approval stages to avoid reducing its objective to a mere pre-project legal formality.

2.8.4 Circular Economy Theory (CET)

In the construction industry, the idea of the circular economy (CE) is becoming more and more of a policy priority. Afshari and Górecki (2019) explained that it is an economic approach that aims to maximise resource use and reduce waste. He buttressed further that in the conventional linear economy, a "take, make, dispose" paradigm of production is obtainable and this contrasts with the Circular economy theory which is inherently a cyclical strategy. In support of this argument, Ghufran et al. (2022) explains that circular economy theory advances the notion of making the most of the lifespan of resources and materials used in construction projects through recycling, renovation, and reuse whenever feasible. This explanation corresponds with that of Guerra, and Leite (2021) who conducted an investigation on the application of the circular economy model to the construction sector in the US, they came the conclusion that open-loop recycling, selective demolition, and prefabrication are the major circular economy strategies employed in the US Architecture, Engineering and Construction sectors. They also suggested that fostering circular economy for sustainable material procurement will involve the use of cultural changes, policies, data accessibility and incentives.

2.9 Gaps in Existing Literature

Existing bodies of knowledge on this subject have mainly investigated the economic implications (Opoku et al., 2022) and environmental implications

(Wong, Chan, and Wade, 2016) of the integration of social responsibility into construction project planning and sustainable material procurement. Much is still left to be explored on the dynamic social implications of the integration of social, especially the implications for the broader community.

Furthermore, there are a number of studies showing the potential benefits of incorporating social responsibility and sustainability into construction projects (Ruparathna and Hewage 2015; Komolafe 2022; Opoku et al. 2022); however, the practical steps for the integration process and the practical ways stakeholders can collaborate are still under-researched. This research topic encompasses an investigation into practical steps to facilitate sustainable material procurement in the construction sector. This gap can be covered by using real-world cases to investigate the practical steps that integration entails.

Finally, another identifiable gap in the existing body of knowledge on this research subject is the lack of extensive discourse identifying the metrics that can be applied to measure the levels of integration of sustainable materials procurement in construction projects. The identification of these metrics will facilitate better sustainable project planning and easier assessment of compliant projects.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

It is standard principle that the purpose of research is to gain knowledge in the specific topic or area of study that could result in a developing new theory, providing a response to a particular problem, validating information and ultimately generating new knowledge (Buchanan, Boddy and McAlman 2013). In order to conduct a research therefore, there must be an identifiable methodology through which the research is undertaken (Pandey & Pandey, 2021). The methodology used for a research refers to the logical and systematic approach to conducting a research (Kumar 2018). It also involves all the strategies, methods, and the philosophy underpinning of the chosen methods and techniques used to gather data and interpret the data in the light of providing answers to the research questions (Flick 2015).

The entire research methodology must always correspond with and align for the fulfilment of the research aim and objectives. Hence, the table below is used to call to mind the aim and objectives of the proposed research.

Table 3.1 Research Aim and Objectives

RESEARCH AIM
The aim of this research is to investigate the manner in which sustainable material procurement guarantees the seamless integration of social responsibility and sustainability principles into the planning of construction projects.
RESEARCH OBJECTIVES
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Assess the current state of the construction industry, highlighting the social, economic and environmental dimensions of construction projects.2. Evaluate the current attitude of the construction industry to social responsibility and Sustainability practices.3. Consider how sustainable methods of material procurement affect the sociological, ecological, and economic aspects of construction projects.

4. Identify the principal stakeholders in construction projects and evaluate how they contribute to the procurement of sustainable materials.
5. Analyse the obstacles stakeholders faced while implementing sustainable material procurement initiatives within construction projects and offer suggestions.
6. Describe the standards used to assess the extent of the integration of sustainable and socially responsible material procurement practises into construction projects.

It is noteworthy that research methodology serves the purposes of increasing the validity of the research, ensuring the research is presented in a systematic method, and guides data collection, among others. This chapter presents the proposed research philosophy, research design, data collection methods, sampling, data analysis, validity and reliability of findings, plan and timeline for investigation, research limitations, and the ethical considerations (Bryman 2016). The 'research onion' coined by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) will guide the discussions under this heading. It is a figurative term that abridges the entire stages and aspects involved in research methodology, each layer represents the different process/stage of the research process.

Figure 3.1 Research Onion Source: Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019)

3.1 Research Philosophy

The quality of a research is determined by the researchers' comprehension of the underlying philosophy (Al-Saadi, 2014). Therefore, it is important first of all establish the entailment of research philosophy. Tamminen and Poucher (2020) define research philosophies as the assortment of vital assumptions that motivate the planning and execution of a research project. Various research philosophies offer diverse viewpoints on how to understand research. The chosen research philosophy is the foundation that determines the processes and stage of the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2019). Research philosophies, to put it simply, are a set of assumptions and beliefs about how knowledge is created (Žukauska et al., 2018). These assumptions could be epistemological, Ontological or axiological (Scotland 2012; Maarouf 2019).

3.1.1 Philosophical Assumptions

Figure 3.2 Philosophical Assumptions. Source: Derived from Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016)

Each philosophical assumptions aims to convey the observations of a research in a distinctive way (Palagolla, 2016).

Epistemological assumptions

A careful examination of knowledge and a specific notion of what knowledge includes and how we come to know what we know are the major characteristics of epistemological assumptions (Hamlyn 1995; Crotty 1998). According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009), epistemology borders on what amounts to acceptable knowledge in the field of the topic under research. An understanding of epistemological assumption aids the

developing of effective strategies for knowledge management (Sanders, Lewis and Thornhill 2019).

Ontological assumptions

Ontological assumption is another core assumption. The question of "what kind of world we are investigating, with the nature of existence, with the structure of reality" is what is addressed by ontological assumption (Crotty 2003). This assumption is based on the idea that the phenomena being studied should be rooted in what exists (Bryman 2004). According to Bryman (2008), the philosophical question of ontology examines the nature of social beings, examining whether they are or can be objective beings that exist independently of social actors or whether they are social constructs that result from the perceptions, actions, and conclusions of the people who make up society. Ontology, to put it briefly, is the study of our beliefs on the nature and kind of reality as well as the social world (Al-Saadi 2014).

Axiological assumptions

Axiological assumptions examine the function of societal values and also the prejudices that shape the narrative and interpretation of a research subject or phenomenon. The axiological dimension takes into account the aims, goals, declarations of mission, opinions, and views expressed by the subjects of the study as well as the researcher's conclusions (Orlikowski and Baroudi 1991). According to Kulinska (2016), axiological research makes the assumption that preconceptions affect the researcher's view and comprehension including the behaviours of those under study.

Methodological assumptions

These assumptions take into account the manner in which the research was undertaken, and the language used (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016). The researcher uses facts to support or disprove any conclusions made just based on observations. Popa (2012) identifies three fundamental principles that are found in methodological assumptions. The primary assumption is

that people's perceptions of value influence their preferences. Secondly is the principle that people make the most of their available resources. Finally is the principle that the behaviours of people differ depending on the knowledge they are exposed to.

Justification of the choice of ontological and epistemology assumptions

From all that has been presented, this proposed research will benefit greatly from a balanced blend of both ontological and epistemology assumptions. Applying the ontological assumption will help the researcher understand and dig deeply into the underlying principles of the concepts of social responsibility, sustainability, and sustainable material procurement. This is expedient especially because there is no single accepted definition for these ideas, and their applications may vary depending on the circumstances at hand (Randhawa and Kumar (2017)). Also, ontology would be useful in exploring the roots of the challenges and gaps in the integration of socially responsible practices into construction projects.

Using epistemological assumptions, the researcher will be able to analyse the prevailing approach to sustainable material procurement in the construction industry. An epistemological viewpoint enables the systematic justification of research data as well as the evaluation of the reliability and validity of research findings (Al-Saadi 2014). When evaluating the relevance and applicability of research findings to the creation of policy and actual implementation, an epistemological approach is helpful (Usher 2002).

3.1.2 Overview of Research Philosophies

According to Muhaise et al (2020), the five main research philosophies include: positivism, interpretivism, Postmodernism, pragmatism, and critical realism.

3.1.2.1 Positivism

This philosophy refers to the naturalist's philosophical viewpoint, which entails creating laws-like generalisations from an observed social reality (Giorgi 2009). The meaning of what is "posited" or "given" is referred to as "positivism" (Muhaise et al. 2020). Ketokivi and Mantere (2010) assert that the positivist approach is rigorously scientific empiricist and aims to produce accurate information free from biases or human interpretations.

3.1.2.2 Interpretivism

Based on the criticisms of positivism, interpretivism emerged (Alharahsheh and Pius 2020). Interpretivism is a subjective standpoint that is based on the argument that interpretivism is more concerned in in-depth variables and context-related features since humans construct richer meanings than physical phenomena (Niglas 2010). The idea that humans cannot be examined in the same way as physical facts and events is reinforced by this. (Alharahsheh and Pius 2020). The interpretivism versions based on Littlejohn and Foss (2009) include: Hermeneutics, Phenomenology and Symbolic Interactionism. Hermeneutics is the study of how to read and comprehend philosophy. The main sources are from the Bible and works of wisdom. The goal of phenomenology is to understand the world by direct observation of events. Last but not least, symbolic interactionism views symbols as communal items that contribute to shared meaning. On the basis of this concept, it is hypothesised that symbols provide methods for assisting in the production of reality (Alharahsheh and Pius 2020).

3.1.2.3 Postmodernism

In an effort to challenge established wisdom and give voice to alternative, underrepresented ideas, postmodernism emphasises the significance of language and power dynamics (Watson 2011). Dye (2013) avers that Postmodernism is closely linked with the ideas of post-structuralism in history (post-structuralism questions fixed meanings and highlights complexity in language and culture). Ontological, epistemological, and ethical norms are challenged by postmodernism, which also makes room

for various discourse, the acceptance of minority and marginalised ideas and practises (Tesar et al. 2021).

3.1.2.4 Pragmatism

Pragmatism considers theories, conceptions, ideas, hypotheses, and research outcomes in terms of their functions as tools for thought and action, as well as the practical ramifications they have in specific situations (Elkjaer and Simpson 2011). It does this by avoiding to address contentious philosophic issues and aims to bring evidence and values, objectivism and subjectivism, precise and thorough information, and many context-sensitive experiences into harmony (Creswell and Clark2017).

3.1.2.5 Critical realism

As a substitute to the more prevalent paradigms of positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism, Critical realism was introduced, therefore, it is a relatively of recent origin and strong philosophical paradigm. Muhaise et al. (2020) explained that critical realism illustrates what we see and feel in relation to the fundamental realities that motivate and determine what can be seen (Lawani 2021).

In the light of philosophical assumptions, the major research philosophies are compared in the table below.

Table 3.2 Comparison of Research Philosophies in the light of Philosophical Assumptions:

Research Philosophy	Ontological assumptions	Epistemological assumptions	Axiological assumptions	Methodological assumptions
Positivism	-A real, objective, and external world that exists independently of individual perceptions or beliefs.	-Relies on scientific method as a systematic approach to research - holds that knowledge should be based on observable and	Value-neutrality research-researchers should strive to maintain independence, eliminate	Involves the use of large samples, measurements, usually quantitative methods of analysis, usually deductive, highly

		measurable facts or phenomena	personal values and biases,	structured, but a variety of data can be examined (survey, experiment, quasi experiment).
Interpretivism	- admits that there can be various, valid opinions.	- recognises that knowledge is subjective and determined by circumstances.	-holds that the perspectives of both the researcher and the participants is significant to the research process and eventual outcomes	- interviews and observations are often relied upon to explore the subjective meanings people attach to their experiences.
Critical realism	- believes that reality is external to our human interpretations.	- Acknowledges that there are underlying structures that produce the recognisable occurrences.	- holds that researchers should aim to be objective in the research process, not imposing their own values.	- Involves moving beyond mere description or correlation to understand the underlying that produce recognisable patterns.
Postmodernism	- Frequently denies the concept of unchanging realities.	- It involves paying attention to omissions, and repressed meanings and interpretations,	Value-based research a researcher and research that is entangled with power dynamics at the expense of other research narratives, some are suppressed and silenced. Extreme	In-depth investigations of anomalies and absences that are typically deconstructive — reading texts and realities against one another a variety of data kinds, generally using qualitative analysis methods

			reflexivity in the researcher.	
Pragmatism	The applications of ideas constitute "reality." Changes in procedures, knowledge, and customs	Values practical experiences and empirical evidence as foundational for understanding the world.	That the axiological premise is that research should have a purpose and provide results that are useful to people, organisations, or society at large.	Emphasises the need of formulating clear research challenges or questions at the outset and adjusting research methods to best address these issues.

Source: Derived from Muhaise et al. (2020)

3.1.2.1 Justification for applicable philosophy.

Given that the purpose of the proposed study is to investigate how effectively incorporating the concepts of social responsibility and sustainability into the design of construction projects. Combining positivist and interpretive approaches will help the research's goals and objectives be realised. Roth and Mehta (2002) averred that despite the presumption that positivist and interpretivist analytical methods are irreconcilable as methods of inquiry and frames of reference for understanding phenomenon, their variants can be merged in the analysis of contentious events. They argued further that doing so advances the objectives of both methodologies by bringing in data that could have been overlooked from using only one viewpoint.

Positivism seeks objective, measurable facts (Alharahsheh and Pius 2020). As a result, it supports the goal of evaluating the effectiveness of integrating sustainability and social responsibility concepts in a methodical and quantifiable way. It would also be applicable to assess the prevailing approach to sustainable material procurement in the construction industry since positivism seeks to identify broadly applicable patterns and trends to develop generalisations that make findings useful for evaluating standard

business practices from a wider perspective (Giorgi 2009). Furthermore, the hallmark of positivism is the ability to gain accurate information free from biases or human interpretations (Ketokivi and Mantere 2010), is useful to carry out an evidence-based analysis of the effectiveness of sustainable material procurement. Positivism is beneficial in evaluating the metrics used to measure the integration of sustainable materials procurement in construction projects through the collecting and analysing of quantitative data related to metrics and measurement practices used in construction projects.

Interpretivism on the other hand acknowledges that there can be multiple, valid realities. Different individuals or groups may have their own unique interpretations and perspectives on a particular phenomenon (Niglas 2010). For stakeholders, qualitative techniques like focus groups and interviews can yield insightful data. Consequently, it would be helpful to identify the important parties participating in building projects and the duties they must carry out to ensure the integration of sustainable material procurement in construction projects. It would be beneficial to critically evaluate the difficulties stakeholders have implementing sustainable material procurement in building projects and offer solutions to these difficulties. With stakeholders, qualitative techniques like focus groups and interviews can yield insightful data.

3.2 Research Approach

The choice of research approach is influenced by the research philosophy, and this in turn creates a connection between the theoretical structure and the research process (Bryman and Bell 2016). The approach can be either deductive or inductive. Deductive reasoning involves a movement from the larger body or the general to the specific. That is, moving from a theory to hypotheses derivation, testing of the hypotheses. For instance, one might start off using a theory, extrapolate hypotheses from it, test those assumptions, and then, after the findings of those tests are known, validate

the theory (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach 2018; Nola and Sankey 2007). Inductive reasoning entails moving from individual cases to a wider context, like when one collects real-world information about a problem and then creates theories and frameworks based on these observations (Locke 2007).

Figure 3.3 Comparison between Inductive and Deductive Reasoning. Source: Trochim and Donnelly (2006)

3.2.1 Justification for choice of Inductive and Deductive Reasoning

For this research, both inductive and deductive reasoning would be more appropriate due to the dynamics of the research's aim and objectives. For instance, assessing the prevailing approach to sustainable material procurement and identifying the strengths and gaps would involve deductive reasoning by starting with a theories related to sustainable material procurement and social responsibility in construction, deriving hypotheses from this theory that can be tested using empirical data, and conducting quantitative analysis to confirm or refute these hypotheses. Understanding the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders based on empirical observations can be accomplished through inductive reasoning which leads to the gathering of real-life data on stakeholder responsibilities, metrics, and challenges related to sustainable material procurement. This

data can then be used to identify emerging patterns or concepts to develop new theories or frameworks based on these observations. Deductive reasoning can be used to assess predefined metrics, but inductive reasoning can help identify additional, context-specific metrics that used to measure the integration of sustainable materials procurement in construction projects.

3.3 Research Methods

Methods	Key features	Advantages	Limitations
Quantitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The focus of quantitative research is on numerical information and facts that can be quantified and expressed in numerical form. This information is frequently gathered using well-structured questionnaires, tests, or observations. Large sample sizes are frequently used in quantitative studies to ensure statistical validity and the capacity to extrapolate results to a larger population. Rigid statistical analysis is used for quantitative data. In order to derive inferences and spot patterns or links in the data, statistical tests and techniques are applied. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative research allows for precise measurement and analysis, leading to reproducible results. Emphasises objectivity and makes an effort to reduce the impact of the researcher's own prejudices. Helps to easily identify patterns and existing relationships. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The rigidity of quantitative research designs can make it difficult to adjust to unanticipated results or add additional factors to the investigation. Poor comprehension of the bigger picture or the "why" of observable patterns.
Qualitative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Frequently employed, especially when little is known about a phenomenon, to investigate novel areas, develop ideas, or give a thorough description of it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enables a more thorough investigation of complicated events and human experiences. A thorough understanding can be provided by researchers' 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Due to the reliance on participant and researcher interpretation in qualitative research, subjectivity and prejudice are possible.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative researchers collect data using techniques like focus groups, interviews, observations, and content analysis. These techniques are versatile and flexible in relation to the research context. 	<p>detailed insights into the "how" and "why" of a specific phenomenon.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Findings are context-specific and often cannot be generalized to a broader population. Demands a lot of resources, including time, money, and knowledge from the researchers to gather, transcribe, and analyse the data.
Mixed Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A combination of qualitative and quantitative research components. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> comprehensive understanding of the research inquiry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conducting mixed methods research can be more complex and time-consuming. Resource Intensive because it requires more resources

Table 3.3 Research Methods. Source: Adapted from Watson (2015); Egawa and Akita (2021); Williams (2007); and Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016).

3.3.1 Justification for choice of mixed methods.

Since the plan of the proposed research is to combine inductive and deductive reasoning, quantitative methods typically follow deductive approaches, whereas qualitative methods are typically associated with inductive approaches (Caruth 2013), the research methods would invariably be a blend of quantitative and qualitative methods, that is, mixed methods.

Vivek (2023) stated that the general rationale behind using the mixed method is to combine and maximise the strengths of both methods for deeper insight while also minimising their weaknesses. According to him, the mixed-methods research approach is targeted at overcoming the limitations attached to choosing either qualitative or quantitative research methods. Östlund et al. (2011) highlighted the incapacity of qualitative research to be generalised and the failures of quantitative research to

reflect the multifaceted nature of human behaviour and perspective as the major limitations of electing to use either of the methods.

The proposed research includes an investigation into various elements, including social responsibility, construction project planning, and the procurement of sustainable materials. Mixed methods are best suited for research such as this, which involves complex subjects. Furthermore, although quantitative data can provide a general picture of trends and practises, qualitative research will be required to fully understand the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders. Also, the Convergent parallel design under mixed method would be applied, this design entails gathering and concurrently evaluating qualitative and quantitative data, with outcomes compared and integrated into the final evaluation (Demir & Pismek 2018; Creswell and Plano 2018).

3.4 Research Strategy

Figure 3.4 Research Strategies Source: Derived from Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016).

3.4.1 Overview of the Main Research Strategies

Research strategies are a vital aspect of research methodology that encompasses the plans and strategies employed by the researcher to gather, interpret and analyse data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016). Case study strategy, according to Robson (2002), and cited by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019), refers to a practical investigation of a specific contemporary event in its actual setting while utilising a variety of sources of evidence. Action research strategy is an approach frequently used in social sciences that involves concurrently taking action and carrying out research to bring about radical change (Beaulieu 2013). Archival strategy refers to the study of historical documents, particularly those produced at a time in the recent past (Mills and Helms 2018). These records give access to the institutions, people, and events that occurred at that earlier period that we might not have had the access to (Ventresca and Mohr 2017). Ethnography is an aspect of anthropology where various cultures are methodically examined. This strategy explores cultural elements by taking the viewpoint of the people being investigated (Hammersley 2018). Grounded theory is the research strategy that aims to create a theory using data that has been methodically collected through comparative analysis (Chun, Birks and Francis 2019). An experiment is a procedure for collecting data proposed to test hypotheses under carefully monitored circumstances with the objective of eliminating challenges to internal validity. Surveys (Questionnaires) are a set of questions designed to gather certain information from a particular group of people, most often quantitative data (Groves et al. 2011). Interviews are typically qualitative; in a qualitative interview, questions are posed in order to elicit information.

3.4.2 Justification for the Choice of Strategies

This research proposes to adopt survey strategies particularly qualitative semi-structured Interviews and quantitative online surveys will be used to address the objectives of the research. Quantitative online survey would be appropriate to gather data on prevailing approaches to sustainable material

procurement, as well as to assess the environmental, social, and economic effects of sustainable material procurement in construction projects. The online survey will also be useful to evaluate the metrics used to measure the integration of sustainable materials procurement in construction projects. The quantitative research design is suitable for this study because it assures the timely and effective collection of relevant data (Rahman, 2020).

Qualitative interviews would be used to identify and understand the key stakeholders involved in construction projects, their responsibilities and the challenges they face in the integration of social responsibility and sustainability to material procurement in construction projects. Qualitative interviews allow for in-depth investigation from gathering varied perspectives (Brinkmann 2013).

3.5 Time Horizons

Cross-sectional and longitudinal studies are the two primary time ranges identified by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016). Cross-sectional studies gather information at a certain time and offers a picture of the topic being investigated. Longitudinal studies gather information from the same people or units over an extended period of time.

Cross-sectional time horizon is the proposed time horizon for this research. Pandis (2014) averred that when compared with longitudinal studies, cross-sectional studies are conducted quicker and tend to be more cost-effective to conduct than longitudinal studies. It was also argued that it provides a snapshot of a specific point in time, and provides useful insights without the need for extended data collection periods. Using this time horizon, structured interviews and online surveys will be used to obtain information from stakeholders of the construction industry at a single point in time.

3.6 Data collection

The general data collection approach employed for the research and the calibre of the data gathered are directly related (Kabir 2016). Primary data collection methods and Secondary data collection methods are the two main categories of data gathering techniques used in research (Taherdoost 2021). The methods for data collection is usually tailored after the chosen research method, design and approach, and should be in sync with the research aims and objectives (Sanders et al. 2016). For the research, both primary and secondary data are proposed. A thorough research is made possible by the use of both primary and secondary sources of information, particularly when they are mixed (Mazhar et al. 2021).

3.6.1 Primary data

Primary data are facts that have been obtained directly from individuals, occasions, or other sources that have a direct bearing on the subject of the study (Kabir 2016). Utilising primary sources aids the gathering of excellent data that can enhance outcomes. Focus groups, surveys, questionnaires, official reports, observations, and interviews are main types (Paradis et al. 2016). The primary methods proposed and the justification for same are discussed below.

Semi-structured interviews- this method is appropriate for this research because it is a good way to solicit qualitative data from key stakeholders in the construction industry. It allows interviewees to elaborate on their comments and answer further probing questions (Sanders et al. 2019). The questionnaire presented in the Appendix A, consists of five (5) open and semi-open questions that are structured to address cogent aspects of the research aim and objectives.

Online surveys- Online surveys are structured questionnaires that people in the target audience reply to online, generally by filling out electronic forms (Braun 2002). An online survey is appropriate for this research due to its cost effectiveness and ability to cover a wider range of survey

participants (Salmons 2021). This is very useful, especially in research on the construction industry, because there are numerous stakeholders involved in the construction industry (Srinivasan and Dhivya 2020). The proposed survey questions are presented in Appendix B.

3.6.2 Secondary data

Secondary sources of data are the sources that offer second-hand data and sources such books, journal papers, publications, reports, newspaper stories, websites, and so on that contain analysis by other academics (Paradis et al. 2016). Usually, the dependability of the research findings is increased by the use of secondary data to support or contradict the primary data (Mazhar et al. 2021). The afore-listed secondary data sources are proposed for this study.

3.6.3 Sampling technique

According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016), the two basic methods for choosing samples in research are probability sampling and non-probability sampling. In probability sampling, each component of the population is given a fair and equal chance to be chosen. It entails a variety of techniques, including stratified sampling, cluster sampling, simple random sampling, and systematic sampling. Non-probability sampling, on the other hand, is used when access is restricted or it is difficult to identify every member of the population. It encompasses Convenience sampling, quota sampling, purposive sampling, and snowball sampling.

3.6.3.1 Justification for Purposive Sampling Technique

For this research, non-probability purposive sampling will be employed. The use of this technique justifies generalisations drawn from the study's sample (Sharma, 2017). Purposeful selection of literature that add to the comprehension of the research problem and that are consistent with the aim and objectives of the study is accomplished through the use of deliberate sampling. Also, it aids selection of participants for the online

survey who are to be stakeholders within the construction industry (such as Architects, Engineers, Contractors, and Clients, among others)

3.7 Data analysis

For the mixed methods proposed, the convergent data analysis is projected. In this approach, quantitative and qualitative data will be collected and analysed independently, and the results thereafter compared and contrasted to identify patterns or discrepancies will be suitable for this research.

For the quantitative data obtained from the online survey, exploratory data analysis method will be used incorporating data visualisation techniques. This would be carried out by the use of diagrams that show patterns, trends, and anomalies in the data collection. Histograms, pie charts, box graphs, scatter charts are typical of this analysis technique (Komorowski et al. 2016).

Figure 3.5 Qualitative Data Analysis Types
Abdulkareem (2018)

Source:

The interviews and interactions will be subjected to thematic analysis to identify key themes and patterns. These themes will then be categorised into categories that are pertinent to the research issues. Thematic analysis will provide and in-depth understanding of the major research areas, and assists in theory building and proffering recommendations (Javadi and Zarea 2016).

3.8 Ethical considerations and Limitation

When using the mixed technique, there are a variety of ethical issues to take into account. Ethical issues including the respondents' informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity.

Informed consent

Getting informed consent from each participant is crucial when gathering primary data through surveys (Fields and Calvert, 2015). The survey

questions are followed by a consent request to make sure of this. Additionally, respondents are made aware of the goal of the study and given the choice to voluntarily withdraw from the survey at any time.

Anonymity and Confidentiality

According to Kamanzi and Romania (2019), maintaining confidentiality is the practice of ensuring that personal information of the study participants are kept confident and is open to those with approval. Through the use of anonymity, researchers may ensure that study participants' identities are kept secret at all times (Sim and Waterfield, 2019). The data received from respondents is kept objective by maintaining both confidentiality and anonymity (Hassn et al., 2021).

Limitations

Online surveys have limited ability to be generalised, they sometimes lack depth, they also encounter vulnerability to subjectivity in selection and individual responses, lack of interest, fraud, and data privacy concerns (Nayak and Narayan, 2019). Interviews tend to be time consuming and resource-consuming Kendall (2014).

3.9 Timelines

A research timeline serves as a well-organized roadmap that outlines the key stages and activities of a research project, starting from its initial concept and continuing through to the final dissemination of findings (Saunders et al., 2016). Crafting a thoughtful timeline plan is essential for researchers as it helps with time management and ensures that the research stays on track within the given resource and time constraints. The Gantt chart illustrating the research schedule is presented below:

Figure 3.6 Gantt chart

3. 10 Summary of Methodology Framework

Figure 3.7 Methodological framework

CHAPTER FOUR

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

4.1 Conclusion

This extended research proposal set out to discourse the integration of social responsibility into construction project planning by conducting a study specifically on sustainable material procurement. The literature review section showed that there are a range of social, economic, and environmental impacts of construction projects. The materials used for many construction projects such as steel, wood or cement generate significant greenhouse gas emissions. There are also concerns over the economic resources expended on waste management, material procurement and on the running and management of construction projects. In the social arena, there are concerns about the diseases caused by poor waste management of construction wastes and other social irresponsibility issues such as forceful land acquisition by the Government and the displacement of local residents during the construction process.

The numerous environmental, social and economic impacts of construction projects amplify the need for increased intentionality all through the phases of construction projects. The construction industry needs to adopt sustainable practices and socially responsible policies that enhance its social responsibility stance. Sustainable material procurement is very instrumental in addressing this challenge because it goes a long way in determining the overall performance of the construction project. The far-reaching impacts of the industry imply that promoting sustainability within the industry especially as it relates to the wide spectrum of projects in the industry will have a consequent positive impact on other related sectors and industries.

It was also revealed that incorporating sustainability in construction projects will involve all the stakeholders involved in the construction process. Stakeholders such as Engineers, Architects, Project managers,

Building Contractors, among others. Encouraging environmental-friendly procurement for construction processes will involve cogent factors such as satisfying client expectations, complying with required environmental regulations that function to alleviate adverse environmental concerns associated with construction, and satisfying requirements of Non-Governmental Organizations on social environmental and economic basis.

On the barriers to integrating of social responsible practices into construction project planning, the review of literature shows that there are both extra-organisational barriers (barriers arising outside an organisation) and intra-organisational referring to the barriers within an organisation. The intra-organisational barriers discussed focuses on how organizations handle sustainability using their internal methods, systems, and resources. While the extra-organisational domain centres on external stakeholders and their influence on sustainability efforts.

Finally, the chapter highlighted that there are still gaps in existing body of knowledge on this research area. First that much is still left to be explored on the dynamic social implications of the integration of social, especially the implications for the broader community. Second that the practical steps for the integration process are still under-researched. Lastly that the metrics that can be applied to measure the levels of integration of sustainable materials procurement in construction projects are not amply addressed by literature.

Chapter presented a justification for the proposed methodology for the research. The proposed research philosophy is to combine positivist and interpretive approaches to help achieve the objectives of the research. This combination brings in data that could be overlooked by using only one viewpoint. In order to ensure a more comprehensive research involving complex subjects, mixed methods is proposed because the research includes an investigation into various elements, including social

responsibility, construction project planning, and the procurement of sustainable materials.

Quantitative online survey would be appropriate to gather data on prevailing approaches to sustainable material procurement, as well as to assess the environmental, social, and economic effects of sustainable material procurement in construction projects. The online survey will also be useful to evaluate the metrics used to measure the integration of sustainable materials procurement in construction projects. The exploratory data analysis method will be used to analyse the quantitative data obtained from the online survey.

Qualitative interviews would be helpful to identify the important parties participating in building projects their roles, and challenges encountered in the integration of sustainable material procurement in construction projects. The interviews would be subject to thematic analysis to identify key themes and patterns. These themes will then be categorised into categories that are pertinent to the research objectives. Thematic analysis will provide an in-depth understanding of the major research areas, and assists in theory building and proffering recommendations.

4.2 Recommendations for further study

1. Undertaking a detailed case studies research of construction projects that have effectively combined social responsibility and sustainable material sourcing should be conducted. It would be useful to identify successful strategies and lessons gained from these projects.
2. Conducting a comparative study of the sustainable material procurement strategies of some large construction companies may provide a more comprehensive understanding of the practical ways to improve the integration of sustainable practices into construction projects.

3. Incorporating a study on the workings of the collaborative efforts among stakeholders that foster integration of social responsibility in construction project planning.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A- Quantitative Online Survey Proposed Questions

1. How familiar are you with materials procurement for construction projects?
 - a. Very Familiar
 - b. Somewhat Familiar
2. Have you ever worked on building projects where acquiring sustainable materials was a top priority?
 - c. Not Familiar
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
3. How would you describe the prevailing approaches to sustainable material procurement in the construction industry?
 - a. Very effective
 - b. Partially effective
 - c. Not effective
4. How do you believe sustainable material procurement practices affect the environmental, social, and economic dimensions of construction projects?
 - a. Positively
 - b. Negatively
 - c. No Impact
5. When compared with the conventional procurement practices, sustainable material procurement is more economically, environmentally and socially beneficial.
 - a. True
 - b. False
6. Do you believe that the integration of sustainability and social responsibilities into construction project planning is a collaborative effort among stakeholders in the industry?
 - a. Strongly agree
 - b. Agree

- c. Disagree
- d. Strongly Disagree

APPENDIX B- Proposed Questions for Semi-structured Interview

1. What role do you play in the planning and execution of construction projects?
2. Have you ever been a part of construction projects keen on sustainable material procurement?
3. What were some of the major highlights of the planning of those projects?
4. What advantages or otherwise can you draw from carrying out construction projects within a sustainable framework?
5. What challenges have you encountered in the process of ensuring construction projects use sustainable materials
6. What parameters do you think to be appropriate to assess how socially responsible construction projects are carried out?
7. What recommendations can you suggest that will aid the integration of sustainability and social responsibility in construction project planning?